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The Relationship Between Brand Value and Social Media: A Research in The Turkish Civil Aviation Sector

Marka Değeri ve Sosyal Medya Arasındaki İlişki: Türk Sivil Havacılık Sektöründe Bir Araştırma

ABSTRACT

Social media, the most crucial component of the digital world, is becoming increasingly integrated with the natural world every day. Marketing activities that manage the interactions between civil airline companies and their customers are critical in this fusion of the modern age. The use of social media in marketing activities makes it easier to adopt airline brands to large masses, and it provides advantages in terms of speed, cost, and scope. This situation will also positively affect the brand value of airline companies that successfully carry out social media activities. The purpose of this research is to determine and interpret the relationship between brand equity and the social media activities of airlines in the Turkish civil aviation sector. The study employed a quantitative research method to test the research model and hypothesis. We collected data by applying questionnaires at Istanbul Airport between 23/03/2024 and 14/04/2024. We conducted explanatory and confirmatory factor analyses and structural equation analyses on the obtained data. The study concluded that consumers engage in social media marketing activities for various reasons, such as entertainment, interaction, fashion following, and personalization. Another significant result of the study is that the factors that positively affect participation are consumers' brand trust and memorable experiences. This result shows that the more consumers' engagement increases, the higher their purchase intention and word-of-mouth tendencies.

Keywords: Brand Value, Social Media Marketing, Turkish Airline Industry.

ÖZET

Sanal dünyanın en önemli bileşeni olan sosyal medya her geçen gün gerçek dünya ile daha da bütünlük bir hale gelmektedir. Modern çağa ait olan bu füzyon sivil havayolu işletmeleri ile müşterilerinin etkileşimlerini yöneten pazarlama faaliyetleri oldukça önemlidir. Pazarlama faaliyetlerinde sosyal medyanın kullanılması geniş kitlelere havayolu markalarının benimsetilmesini hız, maliyet ve kapsam yönlerinden sağladığı avantajlar ile daha kolay bir hale getirmektedir. Sosyal medya faaliyetlerini başarıyla sürdürebilen havayolu işletmelerinin marka değerinin de bu durumdan olumlu yönde etkileyeceği düşünülmektedir. Bu araştırmanın amacı; Türk sivil havacılık sektöründeki işletmelerin marka değerleri ile sosyal medya faaliyetlerinin arasındaki ilişkinin belirlenmesi ve yorumlanmasıdır. Çalışmada oluşturulan araştırma modelinin ve hipotezinin sınanması için nicel bir araştırma yöntemi kullanılmıştır. 23/03/2024 ile 14/04/2024 tarihleri arasında İstanbul Havalimanında anketler uygulanarak veriler toplanmıştır. Elde edilen verilerin analizi için açıklayıcı ve doğrulayıcı faktör analizleri ile yapısal eşitlik analizi yapılmıştır. Çalışma sonuçlarında eğlence, etkileşim, modayı takip ve kişiselleştirme nedenleri ile tüketicilerin sosyal medya pazarlama aktivitelerine katılım gösterdikleri sonuçlarına ulaşılmıştır. Araştırmanın bir diğer önemli sonucu ise katılımı olumlu etkileyen faktörleri, tüketicilerin marka güveni ve hatırlamaya değer tecrübeleri olduğudur. Bu sonuç, tüketicilerin katılımları ne kadar artar ise satın alma niyeti ve kulaktan kulağa iletişim eğilimleri de o derece de arttığını göstermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Marka Değeri, Sosyal Medya Pazarlaması, Türk Havacılık Endüstrisi.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the development and spread of Internet-based mobile communication technologies, people have started to use technological innovations in every aspect of their lives. As a result of these developments, the concepts of interaction and communication have gained another dimension, and social media networks have taken their place in modern life as indispensable figures (Kuzucanlı and Saygın, 2023, p. 417). The rapid increase in the use of social media worldwide (Alalwan et al., 2017, p. 1177), its unique structural features that differ from classical communication tools (Dwivedi et al., 2021, p. 2), and the presence of factors such as users sharing their experiences about businesses on social media (Farivar and Wang, 2022, p. 2) and the impact of these posts on other users have attracted the attention of all businesses (Algharabat, 2018, p. 2). Companies are drawn to social media due to its ability to reach large audiences more quickly and effectively (Shareef et al., 2019, p. 59), at lower costs (Ajina, 2019, p. 1513), its dynamic structure that is easily updated (Yo, 2024, p. 1), and its ability to provide fast feedback (Lal et al., 2021, p. 4). By integrating social media tools into their marketing activities, businesses have gained significant competitive advantages, such as having a presence on major social media platforms, creating shareable content and advertisements, and encouraging customer feedback (Thakur and Thakur, 2018, p. 215).

The movement of passengers, cargo, or mail between two points within the scope of airline transportation is defined as an airline product (Yaşar and Gereade, 2018, p. 173), and the airline market is the place where those who offer the airline product and those who demand it meet and determine the price (Yaşar and Gereade, 2018, p. 174). Civil aviation in Turkey, which made limited progress by the state until the 1980s, started to grow every year with the private airline companies that opened after the liberalization of the domestic market in 1983 and 2003 (Gereade and Orhan, 2015, p. 167; Deniz and Bedir, 2017, p. 173). According to the 2023 Airline Sector Report of the General Directorate of State Airports Authority (GDSAA), total passenger traffic in Turkey reached 213.7 million (excluding direct transit) in 2023, up from 34.4 million in 2003. The report predicts an increase in total passenger traffic of 10.49%, 5.38%, 2.32%, and 2.10% in 2024, 2025, 2026, and 2027, respectively, culminating in passenger traffic of 260 million in 2027 (GDSAA, 2024, p. 2). These data demonstrate the annual growth of the civil aviation sector, which offers significant economic and social advantages to Turkish society and the state.

Social media marketing activities increase brand value and image (Tüfekci et al., 2020, p. 943). This study aims to determine the impact of Turkish airline companies' social media activities on brand value and explain the results. Previous studies in the literature on the Turkish airline industry have examined the impact of brand value on financial income (Okan, 2021), brand image (Karağaoğlu and Ülger, 2021; Konyalılar, 2023) and brand perception (Süzen, 2022) on purchase intention, financial performance research (Kurt and Kablan, 2022), factors affecting passenger attitudes (Eroğlu, 2020), public relations practices in social media (Okmeydan, 2020), the effect of social media activities on brand trust and brand preference (Begtumur and Alizade, 2024), viral marketing brand value relationship (Altay and Çakırkaya, 2023), the effect of technology use on service quality (Konyalılar, 2020), crisis management in social media (Koç, 2020) and marketing communication (Çalışkan and Duygun, 2021), passenger satisfaction (Bakır and İnce, 2024), analysis of online comments (Güngör et al., 2019) topics were addressed. There is no study in the Turkish airline industry on the impact of social media marketing activities on brand value. It is thought that the study's results will benefit the aviation sector and contribute to the literature.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Social Media Marketing

Social media eliminates time and space boundaries to facilitate communication and interaction between marketers and customers (Arklan and Tuzcu, 2024, 424). Social media is defined as an internet-based application platform or mass communication tool that allows users to share content created by users with other users, thus facilitating interaction and collaboration among users (Zachlod et al., 2022; Aichner et al., 2023; Bilgin et al., 2023). People's need for communication has brought the rise of social media, and social activities in the online virtual world are increasing daily with social media (Ardahanlıoğlu and Deniz, 2021, p. 136). Social media marketing refers to marketing activities conducted on social media platforms to promote a product or service, foster brand awareness and loyalty, and enhance brand value (Zarella, 2009; Saravanakumar and Sugantha Lakshmi, 2012; Dwivedi et al., 2015; Wibowo et al., 2020; Khanom, 2023). Social media marketing has been used in tourism (Katsikari et al., 2020), healthcare (Al-Nawafah et al., 2022), banking (Hafez, 2021), civil aviation (Gaber and Elsamadicy, 2021), information technology (Thakur and Arora, 2021), logistics (Orji et al., 2020), energy (Yuen et al., 2023), insurance (Pareek et al., 2022), media (Brigas et al., 2023), hospitality (Pateli et al., 2020), food and beverage (Kumar et al., 2020),

construction (Condie et al., 2024), fashion (Rienda et al., 2021), retailing (Vasiliu et al., 2023), telecommunications (Mansour et al., 2024), education (Raza et al., 2020), and non-profit organizations (Albanna et al., 2022). Social media marketing activities can simplify the purchasing decision process of customers, making it easier for them to make the right decisions (Kotler and Keller, 2018, p. 621) and thus positively improving their attitudes towards the brand or business (Yadav and Rahman, 2018, p. 3885).

Airline companies that communicate and interact with their customers on social media have the opportunity to obtain information about the perception of their services (Park et al., 2020), manage their reputation with proactive communication (Wang et al., 2021), conduct market research with low costs (Ahuja and Alavi, 2018), and reach large audiences effectively, dynamically, and economically through a single channel. In the literature, social media marketing in the aviation industry has been shown to increase brand trust (Seo and Park, 2018; Seo et al., 2020; Begtimur and Alizade, 2024), brand preference (Begtimur and Alizade, 2024), brand value (Masa'deh et al., 2021; Prasetio et al., 2022; Samosir et al., 2023), brand loyalty (Knoblich et al., 2017; Yee et al., 2022; Samarah et al., 2022), consumer motivation (Knoblich et al., 2017; Irshad and Ahmad, 2019; Önen, 2019), purchase behavior (Alnsour et al., 2018; Önen, 2019; Moslehpour et al., 2021), consumer trust (Chan et al., 2020; Seo et al., 2020), service quality (Lee et al., 2018; Tian et al., 2020), customer relationships (Al Balawi et al., 2023; Arul and Tahir, 2023), customer satisfaction (Wahyudi and Parahiyanti, 2021; Nkpurukwe, and Opara, 2022) and brand communication (Çat and Akbulak, 2020).

2.2. Brand Value

A brand is "a name, symbol, or formal expression that shows the main feature of the goods of the producing and selling companies and differentiates them from other competitors" (Mucuk, 2001, p. 136). Today, a brand is an integral part of a product or service in the minds of consumers (Altunşik et al., 2017, p. 87) because customers attach meaning to brands beyond all the features of the product (Armstrong and Kotler, 2013, p. 203). Consumers categorize brands as successful due to their ability to create high levels of brand value (King and Grace, 2009, p. 124). Brand value is a holistic effect that creates additional value beyond the functional benefit of the product or service and differentiates it from other similar products and services as a result of the perception of elements such as brand name, motto, symbol, and smell by the customer (Steenkamp, 2003; Arvidsson, 2006; Melo and Galan, 2011; Goldring, 2017; Gupta et al., 2020; Bar and Haviv, 2023).

Airline branding processes are highly sophisticated and unique. The economic expectations of different passenger classes and the dynamic competitive environment necessitate the continuous evolution of branding projects (Konyalılar, 2023, p. 747). Researchers have already looked at how airline brand value affects people's decisions to buy (Wahyuni and Praninta, 2021; Koech et al., 2023), how it relates to brand management (Samosir et al., 2021; Sezgen et al., 2023), how it relates to promotions (Mahadin et al., 2023), how it affects perceived value (Al-Gharaibah, 2020), how it affects customer loyalty (Ahmad and Worlu, 2019; Phuthong, 2019), how it affects marketing strategy (de Oliveira and Caetano, 2019; Aydın, 2024), and how it relates to service quality (Chen et al., 2019).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study aims to determine the impact of social media activities on brand value in the aviation sector. The study employed the survey technique as a data collection method. We added a question to the questionnaire form to identify individuals who use one or more of the social media elements of airline companies, allowing those who answered yes to proceed with the survey. In the first part of the questionnaire form, there are five questions to determine the demographic characteristics of the participants (gender, age, income level, education level, and marital status). The second part of the questionnaire has 18 propositions, including five sub-dimensions for social media marketing activities. In total, there are 12 propositions on the scale for brand value, including two sub-dimensions. We utilized the scales used in Masa'deh et al.'s (2021) studies to determine brand equity and Seo and Park's (2018) studies to determine social media marketing activities. The questionnaire form assigns weights from 1 to 5 to the response options for the propositions in these sections. We graded these weights as (1) Strongly Disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Neither Disagree nor Agree, (4) Agree, and (5) Strongly Agree. We obtained "Ethics Committee Permission" before applying the questionnaire form. Since the size of the study population was not known precisely, the population sampling calculation chart developed by Neuman (2010, p. 351) was used to calculate the sample. According to Neuman (2010), the minimum sample size was 400 for a population over 1,000,000. We obtained the survey form online between March 23, 2024, and April 14, 2024, by sharing the survey link with Istanbul Airport visitors and creating a link via a QR code. We compulsorily used convenience

sampling while administering the questionnaire. Incomplete and incorrectly completed questionnaires were removed from the completed questionnaire forms, and the data obtained from 862 forms was analyzed using package statistical programs.

Figure 1. Research Model

The research model guides the determination of hypotheses.

Hypothesis 1: Participants' perceptions of social media marketing activities positively affect brand value.

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Participants' Demographic Characteristics

Gender	f	%	Education Status	f	%
Female	387	44,9	Primary/High School	129	15,0
Male	475	55,1	Associate Degree	277	32,1
Marital Status	f	%	Undergraduate	426	49,4
Married	401	46,5	Postgraduate	30	3,5
Single	461	53,5	Age	f	%
Monthly Income	f	%	18-25 years	147	17,1
17002 TL and less	109	12,6	26-35 years	199	23,1
17003-27000 TL	335	38,9	36-45 years	238	27,6
27001- 37000 TL	106	12,3	46-55 years	192	22,3
37001- 47000 TL	131	15,2	56 years and more	86	10,0
47001 TL and more	181	21,0			

44.9% of the participants are female, 55.1% are male, 46.5% are married, 53.5% are single, 15.0% are in primary or high school, 32.1% have an associate degree, 49.4% are undergraduates, and 3.5% are graduates. 12.6% of the participants have an income level of 17002 TL or less, 38.9% have an income level of 17003-27000 TL, 12.3% have an income level of 27001-37000 TL, 15.2% have an income level of 37001-47000 TL, and 21.0% have an income level of 47001 TL or more. 17.1% were between the ages of 18 and 25, 23.1% were between the ages of 26 and 35, 27.6% were between the ages of 36 and 45, 22.3% were between the ages of 46 and 55, and 10.0% were 56 years and older.

Table 2. Factor Analysis Results of Social Media Marketing Activities Scale

	Communality	Factor Load	Eigenvalue	Variance	Mean	Alpha	
Customization 3	0,879	0,893	3,134	18,434	3,309	0,869	
Customization1	0,846	0,873			3,284	0,869	
Customization2	0,799	0,837			3,181	0,869	
Customization4	0,646	0,730			3,047	0,870	
AVE: 0,698 CR: 0,901						3,206	0,906
Entertainment3	0,799	0,865	2,987	17,750	2,892	0,870	
Entertainment2	0,778	0,853			2,983	0,871	
Entertainment4	0,685	0,799			2,958	0,872	
Entertainment1	0,657	0,775			2,974	0,872	
AVE: 0,678 CR: 0,893						2,952	0,876
Interaction 2	0,939	0,909	2,544	14,966	3,278	0,867	
Interaction 1	0,931	0,908			3,272	0,868	
Interaction 3	0,765	0,806			3,331	0,871	
AVE: 0,766 CR: 0,907						3,294	0,918
Word-of-Mouth 2	0,703	0,800	2,038	11,987	3,436	0,874	
Word-of-Mouth 3	0,697	0,761			3,662	0,873	
Word-of-Mouth 1	0,637	0,741			3,290	0,873	
AVE: 0,589 CR: 0,811						3,463	0,748
Trending 2	0,753	0,862	2,002	11,779	3,549	0,881	
Trending 3	0,645	0,784			3,447	0,880	
Trending 1	0,546	0,700			3,549	0,878	
AVE: 0,615 CR: 0,826						3,534	0,722
Total						3,264	0,879

NOTE: Principal component analysis with Varimax rotation. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin sampling adequacy: 84.1%; Chi-Square for Bartlett's test of sphericity: 9448,482, s.d.: 136, p=0.000; n: 862; Overall mean: 3.26; s.d.: 0.728; Al-pha for the whole scale: 0.879; Total variance explained: 74.736% Response categories: 1: Strongly Disagree..... 5: Strongly Agree

In Table 2, the social media marketing activities scale underwent factor analysis to determine its construct validity. The factor analysis revealed appropriate values for KMO sampling adequacy and Bartlett test values. We used the Varimax rotation technique to determine the number of factors, grouping the 17 items in the scale under five factors, which explained approximately 74.736% of the total variance.

The customization dimension consisting of four items explained approximately 18.434% of the total variance; the entertainment dimension consisting of four items explained approximately 17.750% of the total variance; the interaction dimension consisting of three items explained approximately 14.966% of the total variance; the word-of-mouth marketing dimension explained approximately 11.987% of the total variance; and the trending dimension explained approximately 11.779% of the total variance.

A factor requires an item to have a loading of at least 0.450, and we considered the shared variance (concurrence) value to be 0.500. We examined mean-variance explained (AVE) and composite reliability (CR) values to evaluate the measurement model. The CR values should be greater than the AVE values, and the AVE values should be greater than 0.50 (Hair et al., 2017). Examining the communality (>0.500) and factor loadings (>0.400) of the items reveals their appropriate values. Examining the Cronbach Alpha value for the scale's total reliability yields a calculated value of 87.9%, indicating high reliability (Alpar, 2018, p. 548).

Table 3. Brand Value Scale Factor Analysis Results

	Communality	Factor Load	Eigenvalue	Variance	Mean	Alpha
Brand Image 2	0,729	0,854	4,025	33,539	3,959	0,770
Brand Image 5	0,587	0,764			3,826	0,778
Brand Image 1	0,555	0,744			3,700	0,774
Brand Image 6	0,546	0,739			3,686	0,776
Brand Image 3	0,539	0,734			3,784	0,777
Brand Image 4	0,537	0,733			4,096	0,778
Brand Image 7	0,535	0,731			3,989	0,775
AVE: 0,574 CR: 0,904					3,863	0,875
Brand Awareness 3	0,775	0,880	3,363	28,025	3,157	0,760
Brand Awareness 5	0,766	0,875			3,232	0,761
Brand Awareness 2	0,628	0,792			3,186	0,772
Brand Awareness 4	0,597	0,773			3,241	0,773
Brand Awareness 1	0,594	0,770			3,285	0,774
AVE: 0,671 CR: 0,910					3,220	0,877
Total				61,564	3,595	0,788
NOTE: Principal component analysis with Varimax rotation. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin sampling adequacy: 86.6%; Chi-Square for Bartlett's test of sphericity: 4955,093, s.d.: 66, p=0.000; n: 862; Overall mean: 3.59; s.d.: 0.603; Al-pha for the whole scale: 0.788; Total variance explained: 61.564% Response categories: 1: Strongly Disagree..... 5: Strongly Agree						

As shown in Table 3, the factor analysis was conducted to determine the construct validity of the brand value scale, KMO sampling adequacy, and Bartlett test values, which were found to be appropriate. We used the Varimax rotation technique to determine the number of factors, grouping the 12 items in the scale under two factors, which explained approximately 61.564% of the total variance. The brand image dimension, which consists of seven items, explains approximately 33.539% of the total variance, while the brand loyalty dimension, which consists of five items, explains approximately 28.025%. Examining the items reveals that their communality (>0.500) and factor loadings (>0.400) have appropriate values. Examining the Cronbach Alpha value for the scale's total reliability, we calculate it at 78.8% and interpret it as highly reliable (Alpar, 2018, p. 548).

Table 4. The Effect of Social Media Marketing Activities on Brand Value

	Non-Standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Fixed	2,227	0,082		27,309	<0,001
Social Media Marketing Activities	0,419	0,024	0,506	17,202	<0,001
Dependent Variable: Brand Value; R: 0,506; R²:0,256; Adjusted R²:0,255 D-W:1,344 For Model F:295,899 p<0,001					

Table 4 shows the results of the simple regression analysis used to test Hypothesis 1. The model (F = 295.899; p<0.001) is accepted as valid and has valuable values in the estimation process. Participants' perceptions of social media marketing activities significantly explain brand value perceptions. A positive and moderate (r = 0.506) relationship exists between social media marketing activities and brand value (Alpar, 2018, p. 409). Social media marketing activities explain 25.6% of brand value. These results support the acceptance of Hypothesis 1.

Table 5. The Effect of Social Media Marketing Activities Dimensions on Brand Value

	Non-Standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p	Tolerance	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
Fixed	2,263	0,083		27,111	<0,001		
Entertainment	0,007	0,018	0,012	0,373	0,709	0,772	1,296
Customization	0,188	0,020	0,319	9,335	<0,001	0,652	1,533
Interaction	0,064	0,016	0,129	3,907	<0,001	0,740	1,352
Word-of-Mouth	0,130	0,020	0,218	6,404	<0,001	0,696	1,437
Trending	0,014	0,018	0,023	0,745	0,457	0,861	1,161

Dependent Variable: Brand Value; R: 0,555; R²:0,308; Adjusted R²:0,304 D-W:1,384 For Model F:76,248 p<0,001

In Table 5, multiple regression analysis was applied to determine the effect of social media marketing activities dimensions on brand value. The established model (F=76,248; p<0,001) is accepted as valid, and it is seen that it has usable values in the estimation process. A one-unit increase in the customization component of social media marketing activities increases brand value by 0.319 units; a one-unit increase in the interaction component increases brand value by 0.129 units; and a one-unit increase in the word-of-mouth component increases brand value by 0.218 units. Social media marketing activities' entertainment and trending components are expressed as insignificant since the p-value is more significant than 0.05.

Table 6. The Effect of Social Media Marketing Activities Dimensions on Brand Image

	Std. Error		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p	Tolerance	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
Fixed	3,324	0,107		31,100	<0,001		
Entertainment	-0,171	0,023	-0,263	-7,312	<0,001	0,772	1,296
Customization	0,194	0,026	0,294	7,536	<0,001	0,652	1,533
Interaction	0,038	0,021	0,067	1,816	0,070	0,740	1,352
Word-of-Mouth	0,101	0,026	0,147	3,881	<0,001	0,696	1,437
Trending	-0,015	0,024	-0,022	-0,636	0,525	0,861	1,161

Dependent Variable: Brand Image; R: 0,384; R²:0,148; Adjusted R²:0,143 D-W:1,535 For Model F:29,673 p<0,001

As seen in Table 6, multiple regression analysis was applied to determine the effect of social media marketing activity dimensions on brand image. The established model (F=29,673; p<0,001) is accepted as valid and appears to have usable values in the estimation process. A one-unit increase in the entertainment component of social media marketing activities reduces brand image by 0.263 units. A one-unit increase in the customization component increases brand image by 0.294 units, while a one-unit increase in the word-of-mouth component increases brand image by 0.147 units. The interaction and trending components of social media marketing activities are expressed as insignificant since the p-value is more significant than 0.05.

Table 7. The Effect of Social Media Marketing Activities Dimensions on Brand Loyalty

	Std. Error		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p	Tolerance	VIF
	B	Std. Hata	Beta				
Fixed	0,777	0,151		5,139	<0,001		
Entertainment	0,256	0,033	0,254	7,733	<0,001	0,772	1,296
Customization	0,179	0,036	0,175	4,911	<0,001	0,652	1,533
Interaction	0,100	0,030	0,113	3,380	<0,001	0,740	1,352
Word-of-Mouth	0,171	0,037	0,161	4,644	<0,001	0,696	1,437
Trending	0,054	0,033	0,050	1,617	0,106	0,861	1,161

Dependent Variable: Brand Loyalty; R: 0,536; R²:0,287; Adjusted R²:0,283 D-W:1,278 For Model F:69,043 p<0,001

In Table 7, multiple regression analysis was applied to determine the effect of social media marketing activity dimensions on brand loyalty. The model (F = 69,043; p<0,001) is accepted as valid, and it is evident that it has usable values in the estimation process. A one-unit increase in the entertainment component of social media marketing activities increases brand loyalty by 0.254; a one-unit increase in the customization component increases brand loyalty by 0.175; a one-unit increase in the interaction component increases brand loyalty by 0.113; and a one-unit increase in the word-of-mouth component increases brand loyalty by 0.161. The trending components of social media marketing activities are expressed as insignificant since the p-value is more significant than 0.05.

4. CONCLUSION

Brand value is a comprehensive and complex concept. It consists of brand value and customer-oriented and market-oriented brand value. Since customer and market-oriented values are more dynamic elements that are constantly changing, brand value also includes future expectations and related changes. For airlines, this value embodies the consumer's trust and respect, an intangible asset that defies monetary quantification. In civil aviation, a sector characterized by intense competition and strict rules, it is vital for

airline companies to protect and manage their brand value. Social media marketing activities are handy for managing brand value for airlines and all businesses.

According to the study, perceptions of airline companies' social media marketing activities positively affect brand value. This result is also supported by the results of Knoblich et al. (2017), Ahuja and Alavi (2018), Irshad and Ahmad (2019), Kumar et al. (2020), Masa'deh et al. (2021), Moslehpour et al. (2021), Nkpurukwe and Opara (2022), Altay and Çakırkaya (2023), Arul and Tahir (2023), Begtimur and Alizade (2024). Similar results from these studies conducted in different countries before and after the COVID-19 pandemic show that social media marketing is essential, regardless of time and place. Regardless of the domestic or international market, all airline companies that want to be successful and different should carefully manage their social media marketing activities. In future studies, the scope of the research can be expanded and enriched by selecting a population sample in cities other than Istanbul, in sectors other than aviation, and different languages.

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